

**ANALYSIS OF ROAD TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS INVOLVING CYCLISTS IN
SHAHRIKHAN DISTRICT**

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Annotation. Road traffic accidents (RTAs) are one of the most pressing problems of modern society, which cause serious damage to human life, health and the economy. Every year, thousands of people become victims of traffic accidents due to violations of traffic rules, technical malfunctions of vehicles and insufficiently developed road infrastructure. Therefore, it is important to study these incidents and analyze them in depth.

The causes of traffic accidents are diverse, including driver negligence, pedestrians' failure to comply with traffic rules, poor road conditions, speeding and vehicle malfunctions. These incidents lead to serious injuries, material damage and sometimes loss of human life.

Keywords: The role of bicycles in the urban transport system, pedestrian crossings, road accidents involving cyclists

Bicycles today play a unique role in urban transport systems in terms of sustainable development, ensuring environmental cleanliness and promoting a healthy lifestyle. They play an important role not only as an environmentally friendly means of transport, but also in reducing urban congestion, increasing physical activity and ensuring economic efficiency.

Today, in many European cities, such as Amsterdam or Copenhagen, cyclists make up two-thirds of all road users. In other words, for most residents of megacities, using a bicycle is quite possible rather than a car. However, not everyone can ride a bicycle every day, so it is worth considering the bicycle not as a competitor, but as a complement to other types of public transport. Bicycles have great potential, especially when it comes to commuting to and from work[1].

In Germany, 35% of residents of areas far from the center use bicycles to get to work. In Russia, this figure is still known to be less than 1%.

It is widely known that traveling by bicycle in large cities is faster than traveling by car. In a huge city like Moscow, the average speed of cars is from 7 to 11 km per hour. At the same time, in cities with developed bicycle infrastructure, the average speed of a bicycle is 15 km per hour.

There are a number of problems that prevent the widespread use of bicycle transport, which can be divided into 3 main groups:

1. Attitude towards cycling and lack of awareness of its benefits is one of the biggest obstacles to achieving a high share of bicycles in the country.

There are several negative perceptions of bicycles in society.

a) Bicycles are for the poor who cannot afford cars. This perception is a misconception associated with financial circumstances. In fact, the choice of a bicycle is not only related to finances, but also to factors such as a healthy lifestyle, ecology and transport efficiency.

b) It is not a suitable means of transport for women. This perception stems from historical and cultural stereotypes and is outdated in today's modern society. In developed countries, women actively use bicycles for work, study and personal purposes. In the Netherlands, Denmark and many other countries, women are important users of bicycle transport.

c) It is also not suitable for mothers with young children. Because it is not convenient to take children to kindergarten on this type of transport. This opinion may be justified in practical terms, but modern technologies and innovations are helping to solve this problem. Today, many

bicycle companies are developing seats specifically designed for children. They meet safety requirements and allow for comfortable transportation of children. In addition, it is said that society is not aware of how beneficial cycling is for health and the environment[2].

2. Underdeveloped infrastructure creates obstacles to cycling. This reduces people's desire to use this environmentally friendly and healthy mode of transport. Examples of these include:

a) Lack of bicycle lanes. Without bicycle lanes, cyclists are forced to share public roads with drivers and pedestrians. This has some negative impacts. Without dedicated lanes, cyclists are at higher risk of collisions with cars and other vehicles. As a result, people feel unsafe and are discouraged from cycling. Due to the lack of designated lanes, cyclists are unable to separate from the flow of traffic, creating difficult and dangerous conditions (Figure 2.1). b) Lack of bicycle parking spaces. Poorly organized and insufficient bicycle parking spaces increase the risk of bicycles being stolen or damaged. This reduces confidence among drivers (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1. a) Cyclists riding alongside cars in the absence of bike lanes. b) Lack of bicycle parking.

c) Poor road conditions. Poor road conditions create additional challenges for cycling. Poor road conditions can also be detrimental to bicycles. For example, bicycle tires are more likely to be damaged or have higher mechanical failures in areas with uneven roads (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2. Damage to the road surface.

3. There is also the issue of supporting urban development policies. That is, if state or local authorities do not pay enough attention to the development of cycling infrastructure, do not

allocate funds and resources for the construction and maintenance of bicycle lanes, parking lots and other relevant facilities, the level of use of this device will remain low.

It is also important for employers to create minimal conditions to support employees who commute to work by bicycle. This requires taking a light shower and changing clothes after using a bicycle, and for this it is important to organize special places in workplaces. Currently, the lack of places that meet such minimum requirements in employees' buildings hinders the use of bicycles, especially in hot or rainy weather.

In recent years, many measures have been taken in our country to prevent road accidents. However, despite this, it cannot be said that there have been many positive changes in this regard. Unfortunately, some drivers continue to violate traffic rules.

In such circumstances, some specialists and experts are proposing to further increase the punishment. However, this is difficult to achieve the main goal. We mean that it is impossible to prevent traffic accidents without forming a high legal culture among all road users[3].

In conclusion, road accidents involving cyclists occur due to many complex and interrelated factors (infrastructure, human factors, cultural and legal systems). To reduce accidents and ensure the safety of cyclists, a systematic approach is needed, namely, optimization of road design, strict legislation and regular awareness campaigns. At the same time, safety can be significantly improved by developing preventive measures based on modern statistical analysis methods and data. Road accidents involving cyclists occur under the influence of complex and multifaceted factors. The measures implemented in our country are not fully able to achieve the expected positive changes, since the lack of legal culture among drivers and road users and the existing infrastructure deficiencies dominate. Therefore, a systematic and integrated approach is needed to reduce accidents and increase the safety of cyclists.

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